

SPECTRAL PERSYMMETRY OF COMPLEX CIRCULANT AND SKEW-CIRCULANT MATRICES

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ABSTRACT. It is well understood that an $N \times N$ circulant matrix, C , is diagonalised by the standard Fourier matrix. If the resultant eigenvalue matrix $\Lambda = \text{diag}(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_N) = \lambda_1 \oplus \Lambda_{N-1}$, we show how various symmetry properties of C , when real or imaginary, govern exactly the persymmetry properties of Λ_{N-1} . Similarly, we show how symmetry patterns of a real or imaginary skew-circulant matrix, S , dictate the persymmetry properties of its entire eigenvalue matrix. These properties are then used to reveal the spectral persymmetries of complex circulant and skew-circulant matrices, giving a unified classification in which each symmetry type of the matrix is equivalent to a persymmetry type of its spectrum. We note the (classical) consequences for the singular value decomposition of these normal matrices, and present numerical experiments that confirm the classification across all symmetry classes. In the real symmetric and skew-symmetric cases the classification recovers the known reductions to fast cosine and sine transforms.

1. INTRODUCTION

Understanding the eigenvalue distribution of a matrix is useful for tailoring efficient diagonalisation, inversion and multiplication procedures for it. Such procedures are potentially helpful for solving certain problems involving very large matrices. This article focusses upon the spectral properties of square, k -circulant matrices [1, 2] for the two most well-known values of k , namely $k = \pm 1$. Hereafter, for clarity, we shall refer to $+1$ -circulants simply as circulants and -1 -circulants as skew-circulants.

Circulant and skew-circulant matrices are appearing increasingly often in scientific and engineering applications. Briefly scanning the recent literature, one can see their utility is appreciated in the design of digital filters [3], for preconditioning linear systems of equations [4, 5, 6, 7, 8], image manipulation [9], and quantum mechanics [10, 11, 12].

The spectral structure of circulant matrices has been studied by several authors; Davis [2] gives the classical account. Closest to the present work, Karner, Schneid and Ueberhuber [13, 14] treat the spectral decomposition of *real* circulant matrices, and Liu, Chen, Xu and Zhang [15] subsequently derive real Schur forms of real circulant and skew-circulant matrices, tied to the discrete cosine and sine transforms, together with fast real-arithmetic algorithms for matrix-vector products and a DCT–DST variant of the circulant/skew-circulant splitting iteration. A growing body of work has since developed and applied these real DCT/DST factorisations—to block- and g -circulants and to the weight matrices of transformer neural networks [16, 17]. All of this remains deliberately confined to the real field, where the spectrum is centrohermitian and the natural object is a real, block-diagonal Schur form that avoids complex arithmetic.

The present paper is complementary in aim. Rather than eliminating complex arithmetic for real matrices, we classify the persymmetry of the *complex* spectrum across the full range of symmetry types—real, imaginary, symmetric, skew-symmetric, Hermitian and skew-Hermitian—for circulants

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and skew-circulants alike. The persymmetry calculus we work with—the fixing operators $A \mapsto BAB$ and the rules governing combinations of symmetry properties—is due to Pressman [18], who introduced it for general matrices and applied it to their spectra; our contribution is to carry it onto the circulant and skew-circulant families over the complex field. This yields the symmetry-to-persymmetry dictionary of §3 (collected in Table 1), the central role of the operator $G = I_1 \oplus J_{N-1}$ induced by the Fourier diagonalisation, and the exceptional cases of Theorem 3.21. Read componentwise, the circulant half of the classification expresses the classical symmetry pairings of the discrete Fourier transform, and the skew-circulant half their analogues for an odd-time generalised DFT (Remark 3.9); what we believe to be new is their uniform formulation as exact matrix equivalences within the persymmetry calculus, together with the exceptional cases and the complex classification they complete. The real-symmetric and real-skew-symmetric reductions to DCT-I and DST-I used by the authors above are recovered within it as special cases. The consequences for the singular value decomposition of these normal matrices are recorded in §3.6.

Conventions used throughout this paper are as follows. For any square matrix A , we denote A^* as its complex conjugate, A^T its transpose, $A^H = (A^*)^T$ its Hermitian adjoint and A^F its flip-transpose (defined later). All matrices are taken to be $N \times N$ unless otherwise indicated by a capitalised subscript. The vector e_j is assumed to be the j th column of I , the identity matrix, and scalar $i = \sqrt{-1}$. Diagonal matrices are always denoted by Λ , circulants by C , and skew-circulants by S . As usual, A is said to be symmetric if $A = A^T$, skew-symmetric if $A = -A^T$, Hermitian if $A = A^H$ and skew-Hermitian if $A = -A^H$. Matrices possessing no particular symmetry properties will be referred to as general matrices. We assume a priori that all eigenvalues of a Hermitian matrix are real and all eigenvalues of a skew-Hermitian matrix are imaginary.

Section 2 below reviews what is already known about circulants and the matrices required to manipulate them. New results—the symmetry-to-persymmetry equivalences and the exceptional σ -conditioned cases of Theorem 3.21—are presented in §3; §3.6 records the classical consequences for the singular value decomposition. Numerical experiments confirming the classification appear in §4, and conclusions and suggestions for further study in §5.

2. CIRCULANT, FOURIER AND PERMUTATION MATRICES

2.1. Known properties of circulants. Circulant matrices are special members of the Toeplitz family of matrices. Each row of a circulant matrix, C , is a cyclically shifted copy of the previous row, thus, each circulant has at most N distinct matrix elements, $\{c_j\}_1^N$.

Example 2.1. For $N = 5$,

$$C = \text{circ}(c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4, c_5) = \begin{pmatrix} c_1 & c_2 & c_3 & c_4 & c_5 \\ c_5 & c_1 & c_2 & c_3 & c_4 \\ c_4 & c_5 & c_1 & c_2 & c_3 \\ c_3 & c_4 & c_5 & c_1 & c_2 \\ c_2 & c_3 & c_4 & c_5 & c_1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Like all Toeplitz matrices, circulants are persymmetric, that is, they are symmetric about their south-west to north-east diagonal. Algebraically, this is tantamount to suggesting $C = JC^TJ$ where J is the symmetric counter-identity matrix,

$$J = [e_N, e_{N-1}, \dots, e_1] = \begin{pmatrix} & & & & 1 \\ & & & & \\ & & & & \\ & & & & \\ 1 & & & & \end{pmatrix}.$$

Note that J is involutory, $J^2 = I$ (equivalently $J^{-1} = J$).

An important property of circulants is that they are diagonalised by the Fourier matrix [2, 19],

$$FCF^* = \Lambda = \text{diag}(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_N)$$

where F is the symmetric unitary Fourier matrix with elements

$$F_{nm} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \exp(-i2\pi(n-p)(m-p)/N).$$

For the purposes of this paper, integer $p = 1$, a convention that yields [2]

$$F^2 = G \equiv \begin{pmatrix} 1 & & \\ & J_{N-1} & \\ & & \ddots \end{pmatrix} = (F^*)^2.$$

Clearly, G commutes with both F and F^* . In addition, $FG = GF = F^*$ and $F^*G = GF^* = F$.

Lemma 2.2. *G is always involutory and symmetric.*

Proof. Since F is unitary, $G^2 = F^2(F^*)^2 = (F^*)^2F^2 = I$, and since F is symmetric, $G^\top = (FF)^\top = FF = G$. Alternatively, we may rewrite G as a direct sum, $G = I_1 \oplus J_{N-1}$. Then $G^2 = I_1^2 \oplus J_{N-1}^2 = I$ and $G^\top = I_1^\top \oplus J_{N-1}^\top = G$. \square

It is well known (see Davis [2]) that the eigenvalues of a circulant can be found with a single matrix-vector product:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \lambda_1 \\ \lambda_2 \\ \vdots \\ \lambda_N \end{pmatrix} = \sqrt{N} F^* \begin{pmatrix} c_1 \\ c_2 \\ \vdots \\ c_N \end{pmatrix}.$$

FFT techniques [20] can be employed to compute $\{\lambda_j\}_1^N$ with $O(N \log_2 N)$ operations. (This is the strategy underpinning Hager's NAPACK subroutines [21].) A by-product of the classification below is that, for symmetric and skew-symmetric (skew-)circulants, this computation reduces further, to fast trigonometric transforms (Remarks 3.12, 3.17 and 3.19); in the wholly real cases these reductions are known [14, 15].

The other Toeplitz matrix we shall consider in this paper is the skew-circulant, S . Like circulants, skew-circulants are uniquely defined by the elements of their first row.

Example 2.3. For $N = 5$,

$$S = \text{scirc}(s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4, s_5) = \begin{pmatrix} s_1 & s_2 & s_3 & s_4 & s_5 \\ -s_5 & s_1 & s_2 & s_3 & s_4 \\ -s_4 & -s_5 & s_1 & s_2 & s_3 \\ -s_3 & -s_4 & -s_5 & s_1 & s_2 \\ -s_2 & -s_3 & -s_4 & -s_5 & s_1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Skew-circulants are related to circulants via a similarity transform,

$$C = Y^* S Y = \text{circ}(s_1, \sigma s_2, \dots, \sigma^{N-1} s_N)$$

where $Y = \text{diag}(\sigma^0, \sigma^1, \dots, \sigma^{N-1})$ and $\sigma = \exp(i\pi/N)$. Thus, the eigenvalues of S are given by $\Lambda = F Y^* S Y F^*$.

Because of nomenclature, it is tempting to think that a skew-circulant is never symmetric, or that a circulant is never skew-symmetric. However, it is trivial to find cases where the converse holds true.

Example 2.4. For $N = 5$, symmetric and skew-symmetric examples of S are, respectively,

$$\text{scirc}(a, b, c, -c, -b) \quad \text{and} \quad \text{scirc}(0, b, c, c, b),$$

while symmetric and skew-symmetric examples of C are, respectively,

$$\text{circ}(a, b, c, c, b) \quad \text{and} \quad \text{circ}(0, b, c, -c, -b).$$

2.2. Useful permutation matrices. Any $N \times N$ matrix, each row and column of which contains one unit entry and $N-1$ zero entries, we call a permutation matrix. The matrices J and G introduced in section 2 are examples of permutation matrices. For any symmetric involutory permutation matrix, B say, we will adopt the compact notation [18]:

$$A^{[B]} = BAB.$$

It is elementary to show that the “fixing” operator $(-)^{[B]}$ commutes with the transposition, complex conjugate and Hermitian adjoint operators.

Definition 2.5. The following naming conventions will be used throughout the remainder of the article. Matrix A is:

$$\begin{array}{ll} \text{centrosymmetric if } A^{[J]} = A, & \text{skew-centrosymmetric if } A^{[J]} = -A, \\ \text{centrohermitian if } A^{*[J]} = A, & \text{skew-centrohermitian if } A^{*[J]} = -A, \\ \text{persymmetric if } A^{\text{T}[J]} = A, & \text{skew-persymmetric if } A^{\text{T}[J]} = -A, \\ \text{perhermitian if } A^{\text{H}[J]} = A, & \text{skew-perhermitian if } A^{\text{H}[J]} = -A, \\ [B]\text{-fixed if } A^{[B]} = A, & \text{skew-}[B]\text{-fixed if } A^{[B]} = -A, \\ [B]X\text{-fixed if } A^{X[B]} = A, & \text{skew-}[B]X\text{-fixed if } A^{X[B]} = -A, \end{array}$$

where $X = *, \text{T}, \text{H}$.

The permutation matrix J is useful for flip-transposing a matrix, that is, transposing a matrix about its counterdiagonal.

Definition 2.6. The flip-transpose $A^{\text{F}} \equiv A^{\text{T}[J]}$.

Example 2.7. If $A = \begin{pmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{13} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} & A_{23} \\ A_{31} & A_{32} & A_{33} \end{pmatrix}$ then $A^{\text{F}} = \begin{pmatrix} A_{33} & A_{23} & A_{13} \\ A_{32} & A_{22} & A_{12} \\ A_{31} & A_{21} & A_{11} \end{pmatrix}$.

Another useful permutation matrix is the ‘push’ matrix defined by $\Pi = \text{circ}(0, 1, 0, \dots, 0)$. Left-multiplication by Π pushes every row up by one, while right-multiplication by Π^{-1} pushes every column to the left by one. Note that $\Pi^{-1} = \Pi^{\text{T}} = \Pi^{\text{H}} = \Pi^{N-1}$.

Example 2.8. Using A from the previous example,

$$\Pi A = \begin{pmatrix} A_{21} & A_{22} & A_{23} \\ A_{31} & A_{32} & A_{33} \\ A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{13} \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad A\Pi^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} A_{12} & A_{13} & A_{11} \\ A_{22} & A_{23} & A_{21} \\ A_{32} & A_{33} & A_{31} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Similarity transforming a matrix with Π has the effect of pushing its lower right $(N-1 \times N-1)$ submatrix in the northwest direction.

Example 2.9. Given the results of the previous example,

$$\Pi A \Pi^{-1} = \Pi \begin{pmatrix} A_{12} & A_{13} & A_{11} \\ A_{22} & A_{23} & A_{21} \\ A_{32} & A_{33} & A_{31} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} A_{22} & A_{23} & A_{21} \\ A_{32} & A_{33} & A_{31} \\ A_{12} & A_{13} & A_{11} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Remark 2.10. Since a circulant C is constant down each diagonal, $C = \Pi^{\delta} C \Pi^{-\delta}$ where δ is any integer.

Lemma 2.11. *The following statements are true:*

- (i) $\Pi G = J = G \Pi^{-1}$
- (ii) $J \Pi = G = \Pi^{-1} J$
- (iii) $J G = \Pi$ and $G J = \Pi^{-1}$
- (iv) Π is both persymmetric and $[G] \text{T}$ -fixed.

Proof. To show (i) is true, write the LHS in block form and solve:

$$\Pi G = \begin{pmatrix} & I_{N-1} \\ 1 & \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \\ & J_{N-1} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} & J_{N-1} \\ 1 & \end{pmatrix} = J = J^\top = G\Pi^{-1}.$$

Since J and G are both involutory, (i) can be rearranged to give (ii) and (iii). Statement (iv) follows by substituting (i) and (ii) into (iii). \square

Lemma 2.12. *All circulants are $[G]\top$ -fixed.*

Proof. Since $C = \Pi^\delta C \Pi^{-\delta}$ is persymmetric for any integer δ and $\Pi^\top = \Pi^{-1}$,

$$C = J C^\top J = J(\Pi C \Pi^{-1})^\top J = G C^\top G = C^\top [G].$$

\square

Lemma 2.13. *The matrix product $FY^* = JF^*Y$.*

Proof. The push matrix is itself a circulant, $\Pi = \text{circ}(0, 1, 0, \dots, 0)$, so by the eigenvalue formula of §2 its spectrum is \sqrt{N} times the second column of F^* :

$$F\Pi F^* = \text{diag}(\sigma^{2(n-1)})_{n=1}^N = Y^2, \quad \text{whence} \quad \Pi = F^* Y^2 F.$$

Recalling that $\Pi = JG$ and $FG = F^*$, it follows that $J = \Pi G = F^* Y^2 F G = F^* Y^2 F^*$, and therefore

$$JF^*Y = F^*Y^2(F^*)^2Y = F^*Y^2GY.$$

Both Y^2GY and GY^* have their non-zero entries at the positions of G , and the entries agree: trivially in the first row, and in rows $k \geq 2$ (where the entry sits in column $N + 2 - k$) because $\sigma^{2(k-1)}\sigma^{N+1-k} = \sigma^{N+k-1} = \sigma^{(k-1)-N} = \sigma^{-(N+1-k)}$, σ^{2N} being 1. Hence $Y^2GY = GY^*$ and $JF^*Y = F^*GY^* = FY^*$. Equivalently, comparing entries, both FY^* and JF^*Y have (n, m) entry $N^{-1/2} \sigma^{-(m-1)(2n-1)}$. This identity is posed as an exercise by Davis [2, §3.2.1, Problem 7]; the proof above is self-contained. \square

3. SPECTRAL PROPERTIES

In the ensuing subsections, we shall explore the spectral properties of various real, imaginary and complex (skew-)circulants. Before examining these properties in detail, it will prove useful to first understand the effect of similarity transforming diagonal matrices with G .

3.1. $[G]$ -fixed diagonals. For any dense, general matrix A , the result of similarity transformation with G is quite intricate; essentially, three things occur: (i) the lower $N - 1 \times N - 1$ submatrix is similarity transformed with J ; (ii) elements $\{A_{1j}\}_2^N$ are replaced by $\{A_{1j}\}_N^2$; (iii) elements $\{A_{j1}\}_2^N$ are replaced by $\{A_{j1}\}_N^2$.

Example 3.1. For $N = 4$, $A^{[G]} = \begin{pmatrix} A_{11} & A_{14} & A_{13} & A_{12} \\ A_{41} & A_{44} & A_{43} & A_{42} \\ A_{31} & A_{34} & A_{33} & A_{32} \\ A_{21} & A_{24} & A_{23} & A_{22} \end{pmatrix}.$

Fortunately, when dealing with diagonal matrices, performing similarity transformations with G is relatively simple.

Example 3.2. For $N = 5$, $\Lambda^{[G]} = \text{diag}(\lambda_1, \lambda_5, \lambda_4, \lambda_3, \lambda_2).$

Definition 3.3. Let $\Lambda = \text{diag}(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_N) = \lambda_1 \oplus \Lambda_{N-1}$ where $\Lambda_{N-1} = \text{diag}(\lambda_2, \lambda_3, \dots, \lambda_N).$

Lemma 3.4. *The following statements are true:*

- (i) Λ is $[G]$ -fixed $\iff \Lambda_{N-1}$ is centrosymmetric,
- (ii) Λ is $[G]^*$ -fixed $\iff \Lambda_{N-1}$ is centrohermitian and λ_1 is real,
- (iii) Λ is skew- $[G]$ -fixed $\iff \Lambda_{N-1}$ is skew-centrosymmetric and $\lambda_1 = 0$,
- (iv) Λ is skew- $[G]^*$ -fixed $\iff \Lambda_{N-1}$ is skew-centrohermitian and λ_1 is imaginary.

Proof. Handle Λ and G in direct-sum form. (i) If $\Lambda = G\Lambda G$ then $\lambda_1 \oplus \Lambda_{N-1} = \lambda_1 \oplus \Lambda_{N-1}^F$; (ii) if $\Lambda = G\Lambda^*G$ then $\lambda_1 \oplus \Lambda_{N-1} = \lambda_1^* \oplus \Lambda_{N-1}^{*F}$; (iii) if $\Lambda = -G\Lambda G$ then $\lambda_1 \oplus \Lambda_{N-1} = -(\lambda_1 \oplus \Lambda_{N-1}^F)$; and (iv) if $\Lambda = -G\Lambda^*G$ then $\lambda_1 \oplus \Lambda_{N-1} = -(\lambda_1^* \oplus \Lambda_{N-1}^{*F})$. \square

3.2. Constant circulants. Consider a constant circulant $C = \text{circ}(c_1, c_1, \dots, c_1)$ where c_1 is a non-zero scalar. C may be real, purely imaginary or complex. For two reasons C has a single non-zero eigenvalue. Firstly, $\text{rank}(C) = 1$, therefore C must have at least $N - 1$ zero eigenvalues. Secondly, $\text{tr}(\Lambda) = \text{tr}(C) = Nc_1 \neq 0$. It remains to identify where this single non-zero eigenvalue lies in Λ .

Proposition 3.5. *If $C = \text{circ}(c_1, c_1, \dots, c_1)$, $\Lambda = \text{diag}(Nc_1, 0, \dots, 0)$.*

Proof. Define the vector $\mathbf{q} = (1, 1, \dots, 1)^\top$ and rewrite $C = c_1 \mathbf{q} \mathbf{q}^\top$ such that $\Lambda = c_1 F \mathbf{q} \mathbf{q}^\top F^*$. Given

$$\sum_{m=1}^N F_{nm} = \begin{cases} \sqrt{N} & \text{if } n = 1, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

$F\mathbf{q} = \sqrt{N} \mathbf{e}_1$ and $\Lambda = Nc_1 \mathbf{e}_1 \mathbf{e}_1^\top = \text{diag}(Nc_1, 0, \dots, 0)$. \square

3.3. Real and imaginary circulants. We can now record how the symmetry of a real or imaginary circulant is transferred, under the Fourier diagonalisation, into a definite persymmetry of its spectrum—and, conversely, recovered from it. The whole correspondence rests on the following dictionary.

Lemma 3.6. *Let $C = F^* \Lambda F$ be a circulant. Then*

$$C^\top = F^* \Lambda^{[G]} F, \quad C^* = F^* \Lambda^{*[G]} F, \quad C^H = F^* \Lambda^* F.$$

Consequently, since $\Lambda \mapsto F^ \Lambda F$ is a bijection between diagonal matrices and circulants [2],*

$$C = \pm C^\top \iff \Lambda = \pm \Lambda^{[G]}, \quad C = \pm C^* \iff \Lambda = \pm \Lambda^{*[G]}, \quad C = \pm C^H \iff \Lambda = \pm \Lambda^*.$$

Proof. Because F is symmetric and unitary,

$$C^H = F^H \Lambda^H (F^*)^H = F^* \Lambda^* F, \quad C^\top = F^\top \Lambda^\top (F^*)^\top = F \Lambda F^*.$$

Substituting $F = F^* G$ and $F^* = G F$ into the latter gives $C^\top = F^* G \Lambda G F = F^* \Lambda^{[G]} F$. (Equivalently, $C^\top = C^{[G]}$, which restates Lemma 2.12.) Applying the transpose identity to the circulant C^H , whose eigenvalue matrix is Λ^* , gives $C^* = (C^H)^\top = F^* \Lambda^{*[G]} F$. \square

Statements (i) and (v) of the theorem below are sometimes seen in the literature (e.g., [22, 3, 23]) without proof, and then only as one-way implications; we note that every statement is in fact an equivalence.

Theorem 3.7. *Let C be a circulant with eigenvalue matrix $\Lambda = F C F^*$. The following statements are true:*

- (i) C is real $\iff \Lambda$ is $[G]^*$ -fixed,
- (ii) C is imaginary $\iff \Lambda$ is skew- $[G]^*$ -fixed,
- (iii) C is real skew-symmetric $\iff \Lambda$ is imaginary skew- $[G]$ -fixed,
- (iv) C is imaginary skew-symmetric $\iff \Lambda$ is real skew- $[G]$ -fixed,
- (v) C is real symmetric $\iff \Lambda$ is real $[G]$ -fixed,
- (vi) C is imaginary symmetric $\iff \Lambda$ is imaginary $[G]$ -fixed.

Proof. Statements (i) and (ii) are the conjugation equivalence $C = \pm C^* \iff \Lambda = \pm \Lambda^{*[G]}$ of Lemma 3.6. For the remainder, note that $\Lambda^{*[G]} = (\Lambda^{[G]})^*$, so among the three conditions $\Lambda = \varepsilon_1 \Lambda^{*[G]}$, $\Lambda = \varepsilon_2 \Lambda^{[G]}$ and $\Lambda = \varepsilon_3 \Lambda^*$ (signs $\varepsilon_k = \pm 1$), any two imply the third provided $\varepsilon_3 = \varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2$; the same holds on the matrix side for realness, symmetry and Hermiticity of C . Thus, for (iii): C is real and skew-symmetric $\iff \Lambda = \Lambda^{*[G]}$ and $\Lambda = -\Lambda^{[G]}$ (Lemma 3.6) $\iff \Lambda = -\Lambda^*$ and $\Lambda = -\Lambda^{[G]}$, that is, Λ is imaginary and skew- $[G]$ -fixed. Statements (iv)–(vi) follow identically from the sign pairs $(\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2) = (-, -), (+, +)$ and $(-, +)$. \square

Example 3.8. For $N = 4$, the real skew-symmetric circulant $C = \text{circ}(0, a, 0, -a)$ has spectrum $\Lambda = \text{diag}(0, 2ai, 0, -2ai)$, which is imaginary and skew- $[G]$ -fixed (indeed $G\Lambda G = -\Lambda$), illustrating statement (iii).

Remark 3.9. Read componentwise on the first row of C and the diagonal of Λ , Theorem 3.7 restates the classical symmetry pairings of the discrete Fourier transform: a real sequence has a conjugate-even transform, a real even sequence a real even transform, a real odd sequence an imaginary odd transform, and so on [24, 25]. (Evenness and oddness here are with respect to the index reversal $j \mapsto N + 2 - j$ fixing the first index—exactly the action of G .) Theorem 3.14 below plays the same role for the odd-time generalised DFT underlying the skew-circulant diagonalisation; such generalised transforms and their symmetric variants appear in the signal-processing literature [26]. What the persymmetry formulation adds is a uniform matrix calculus in which these pairings hold as exact equivalences and can be composed—via the similarity Y —into the complex classification of Theorems 3.18 and 3.21.

Definition 3.10. When N is even, let $N'_e = N/2 + 1$.

Corollary 3.11. *The following statements are true when N is even:*

- (i) *If C is real, $\lambda_{N'_e}$ is real,*
- (ii) *If C is imaginary, $\lambda_{N'_e}$ is imaginary,*
- (iii) *If C is real skew-symmetric, $\lambda_{N'_e} = 0$,*
- (iv) *If C is imaginary skew-symmetric, $\lambda_{N'_e} = 0$.*

Proof. For even N , the index reversal $j \mapsto N + 2 - j$ of positions $2, \dots, N$ —the action of G on a diagonal—has N'_e as its unique fixed point. Hence a $[G]$ *-fixed Λ satisfies $\lambda_{N'_e} = \lambda_{N'_e}^*$, giving (i); a skew- $[G]$ *-fixed Λ satisfies $\lambda_{N'_e} = -\lambda_{N'_e}^*$, giving (ii); and a skew- $[G]$ -fixed Λ satisfies $\lambda_{N'_e} = -\lambda_{N'_e} = 0$, giving (iii) and (iv) via Theorem 3.7(iii) and (iv). (In cases (iii) and (iv), $\lambda_1 = 0$ as well, by Lemma 3.4(iii).) \square

Remark 3.12. The eigenvalues of general real and imaginary circulants may be computed using a single real \rightarrow complex FFT, which uses about half as many operations as a standard complex \rightarrow complex FFT [25]. For even N , the spectra of (skew-)symmetric real and imaginary circulants can be calculated using fast discrete trigonometric transforms. In the case of real skew-symmetric circulants, $\lambda_1 = \lambda_{N'_e} = 0$ (Lemma 3.4(iii) and the corollary above), so only $N'_e - 2$ imaginary eigenvalues need to be explicitly computed:

$$\text{Im}(\lambda_{j+1}) = \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi k j}{N}\right) c_{k+1} = 2 \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \sin\left(\frac{\pi k j}{m}\right) c_{k+1}$$

where $m = N/2$ and $1 \leq j < m$. These eigenvalues may be computed with a specialised $(m - 1)$ -point DST-I procedure [27, 28] with $O(m \log_2 m)$ operations. Similarly, the spectrum of a real or imaginary symmetric circulant can be acquired by utilising an N'_e -point DCT-I algorithm. For odd N , fast fractional trigonometric transforms [29] may be employed. Such methods rely upon chirping (modulation by a quadratic-phase sequence, as in Bluestein's chirp- z transform [30]) and calls to efficient DCT-I and DST-I procedures.

3.4. Real and imaginary skew-circulants. For skew-circulants the same symmetries induce a persymmetry of the spectrum about its main counterdiagonal—a centro-pattern—in place of the $[G]$ -pattern seen for circulants. The dictionary now reads as follows.

Lemma 3.13. *Let $S = (YF^*)\Lambda(FY^*)$ be a skew-circulant. Then*

$$S^\top = (YF^*)\Lambda^{[J]}(FY^*), \quad S^* = (YF^*)\Lambda^{*[J]}(FY^*), \quad S^H = (YF^*)\Lambda^*(FY^*),$$

and, since $\Lambda \mapsto (YF^)\Lambda(FY^*)$ is a bijection between diagonal matrices and skew-circulants, the analogous equivalences hold: $S = \pm S^\top \iff \Lambda = \pm \Lambda^{[J]}$, $S = \pm S^* \iff \Lambda = \pm \Lambda^{*[J]}$, and $S = \pm S^H \iff \Lambda = \pm \Lambda^*$.*

Proof. The matrix YF^* is unitary, so the third identity is immediate. Transposing, $S^\top = Y^*F\Lambda F^*Y$. Lemma 2.13 states $FY^* = JF^*Y$; transposing and conjugating this identity give $Y^*F = YF^*J$ and $F^*Y = JFY^*$ respectively, whence

$$S^\top = (YF^*J)\Lambda(JFY^*) = (YF^*)\Lambda^{[J]}(FY^*).$$

Applying the transpose identity to the skew-circulant S^H , whose eigenvalue matrix is Λ^* , gives $S^* = (S^H)^\top = (YF^*)\Lambda^{*[J]}(FY^*)$. \square

Statement (i) of the theorem below has been used (as a one-way implication) by Liu and Vaidyanathan [3] for realising digital filters.

Theorem 3.14. *Let S be a skew-circulant with eigenvalue matrix $\Lambda = FY^*SYF^*$. The following statements are true:*

- (i) S is real $\iff \Lambda$ is centrohermitian,
- (ii) S is imaginary $\iff \Lambda$ is skew-centrohermitian,
- (iii) S is real skew-symmetric $\iff \Lambda$ is imaginary skew-centrosymmetric,
- (iv) S is imaginary skew-symmetric $\iff \Lambda$ is real skew-centrosymmetric,
- (v) S is real symmetric $\iff \Lambda$ is real centrosymmetric,
- (vi) S is imaginary symmetric $\iff \Lambda$ is imaginary centrosymmetric.

Proof. Identical to the proof of Theorem 3.7, with Lemma 3.13 in place of Lemma 3.6: the conjugation equivalence gives (i) and (ii), and since $\Lambda^{*[J]} = (\Lambda^{[J]})^*$ the remaining four statements follow from the same sign pairs. \square

Definition 3.15. When N is odd, let $N'_o = (N + 1)/2$.

Corollary 3.16. *The following statements are true when N is odd:*

- (i) If S is real, $\lambda_{N'_o}$ is real,
- (ii) If S is imaginary, $\lambda_{N'_o}$ is imaginary,
- (iii) If S is real skew-symmetric, $\lambda_{N'_o} = 0$,
- (iv) If S is imaginary skew-symmetric, $\lambda_{N'_o} = 0$.

Proof. For odd N , the index reversal $j \mapsto N + 1 - j$ effected by J has N'_o as its unique fixed point. A centrohermitian diagonal therefore satisfies $\lambda_{N'_o} = \lambda_{N'_o}^*$, a skew-centrohermitian one $\lambda_{N'_o} = -\lambda_{N'_o}^*$, and a skew-centrosymmetric one $\lambda_{N'_o} = -\lambda_{N'_o} = 0$; Theorem 3.14 supplies the relevant class in each case. \square

Remark 3.17. For general real and imaginary skew-circulants, unlike their circulant counterparts, using real \rightarrow complex FFTs does not reduce the operation count. The eigenvalues here transform the sequence $\{\sigma^{k-1}s_k\}$, which is complex even when S is real, so the single real transform available for a real circulant does not apply; recovering the spectrum through real transforms would take two of them—the cost of one complex \rightarrow complex FFT—which is therefore the simpler choice. (This is a statement about operation count; we make no claim about wall-clock performance, which depends on the transform implementation.) For even N , due to the lower $N - 1 \times N - 1$ submatrix of Y

being skew-centrohermitian, (skew-)symmetric skew-circulants may be diagonalised efficiently with a combination of DCT-I and DST-I techniques. For example, a real skew-symmetric skew-circulant has $m = N/2$ imaginary eigenvalues that need to be explicitly computed:

$$\begin{aligned} \operatorname{Im}(\lambda_{j+1}) &= \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi kj}{N}\right) \operatorname{Im}(\sigma^k s_{k+1}) + \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi kj}{N}\right) \operatorname{Re}(\sigma^k s_{k+1}) \\ &= \operatorname{Im}((-1)^j \sigma^m s_{N'_e}) + 2 \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \cos\left(\frac{\pi kj}{m}\right) \operatorname{Im}(\sigma^k s_{k+1}) + 2 \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \sin\left(\frac{\pi kj}{m}\right) \operatorname{Re}(\sigma^k s_{k+1}) \end{aligned}$$

where $0 \leq j < m$. The first two terms in the above equation constitute an N'_e -point DCT-I, while the remaining term (which is not strictly necessary for $j = 0$) represents an $(m - 1)$ -point DST-I. Overall, the calculation of these eigenvalues can be achieved with $O(N \log_2 m)$ operations.

3.5. Complex (skew-)circulants. With the real and imaginary (skew-)circulant cases treated above, the analogous properties for the complex cases can now be determined.

Theorem 3.18. *In statements (i) and (ii) below, C is a circulant with eigenvalue matrix $\Lambda = FCF^*$; in statements (iii) and (iv), S is a skew-circulant with eigenvalue matrix $\Lambda = FY^*SYF^*$.*

The following statements are true:

- (i) C is complex symmetric $\iff \Lambda$ is $[G]$ -fixed,
- (ii) C is complex skew-symmetric $\iff \Lambda$ is skew- $[G]$ -fixed,
- (iii) S is complex symmetric $\iff \Lambda$ is centrosymmetric,
- (iv) S is complex skew-symmetric $\iff \Lambda$ is skew-centrosymmetric.

Proof. These are precisely the transposition equivalences $C = \pm C^T \iff \Lambda = \pm \Lambda^{[G]}$ and $S = \pm S^T \iff \Lambda = \pm \Lambda^{[J]}$ of Lemmas 3.6 and 3.13; no reality constraint is involved.

A second route to the forward implications, which we record because Remark 3.19 exploits it, splits the matrix into real and imaginary parts. If C is a complex circulant then $A = \operatorname{Re}(C)$ and $B = \operatorname{Im}(C)$ are real circulants with $C = A + iB$, and $C^T = A^T + iB^T$; hence C is symmetric (respectively skew-symmetric) exactly when A and B are both symmetric (respectively both skew-symmetric). Because $\Lambda = FCF^*$ depends linearly on C , the spectrum splits as $\Lambda = \Lambda_A + i\Lambda_B$, where Λ_A and Λ_B are the spectra of the real circulants A and B . Each summand class in Definition 2.5— $[G]$ -fixed, skew- $[G]$ -fixed, centrosymmetric, skew-centrosymmetric—is closed under addition and under multiplication by i .

For (i), A and B are real symmetric, so Theorem 3.7(v) makes Λ_A and Λ_B real and $[G]$ -fixed; thus $\Lambda = \Lambda_A + i\Lambda_B$ is $[G]$ -fixed. For (ii), A and B are real skew-symmetric, so Theorem 3.7(iii) makes each spectrum skew- $[G]$ -fixed, and hence so is Λ . Statements (iii) and (iv) are identical with S , A , B skew-circulants and Theorem 3.14(v) and (iii) in place of Theorem 3.7, using that centrosymmetry and skew-centrosymmetry are preserved under sums. \square

Remark 3.19. The real/imaginary decomposition recorded in the proof of Theorem 3.18 also makes the symmetric and skew-symmetric complex cases computationally convenient. If C is complex symmetric then $\operatorname{Re}(C)$ and $\operatorname{Im}(C)$ are real symmetric circulants, so by Remark 3.12 each of their spectra is an N'_e -point DCT-I; hence the spectrum of C is obtained from *two* DCT-I transforms, $\Lambda = \Lambda_{\operatorname{Re}(C)} + i\Lambda_{\operatorname{Im}(C)}$. Likewise a complex skew-symmetric circulant needs two DST-I transforms, and the complex (skew-)symmetric skew-circulants reduce, through the same real/imaginary split, to the DCT-I/DST-I combination of Remark 3.17. Relative to the full complex \rightarrow complex FFT this halves the operation count—the saving afforded by the symmetry, though not the further saving available when the matrix is wholly real. (Both circulant reductions were checked numerically to machine precision.) The general, Hermitian, skew-Hermitian and σ -conditioned cases of Theorems 3.7, 3.14 and 3.21 carry no such symmetry in the generating sequence, so no trigonometric reduction applies;

the predicted persymmetry of the spectrum is then a redundancy one may exploit in storage rather than in transform cost.

Corollary 3.20. *The following statements are true:*

- (i) *If N is even and C is complex skew-symmetric, $\lambda_{N'_e} = 0$,*
- (ii) *If N is odd and S is complex skew-symmetric, $\lambda_{N'_o} = 0$.*

Proof. By Theorem 3.18(ii) and (iv), Λ is skew- $[G]$ -fixed (respectively skew-centrosymmetric), and the relevant index reversal fixes the index N'_e when N is even (respectively N'_o when N is odd), forcing $\lambda_{N'_e} = -\lambda_{N'_e}$ (respectively $\lambda_{N'_o} = -\lambda_{N'_o}$). \square

So far, we have seen a general relationship between a (skew-)circulant and its eigenvalues: a circulant often has a $[G]$ -fixed spectrum, while a skew-circulant often has a persymmetric spectrum. However, exceptions to this trend emerge for particular complex non-(skew-)symmetric circulants and skew-circulants.

Theorem 3.21. *In statements (i)–(vi) below, $C = \text{circ}(c_1, \dots, c_N)$ has eigenvalue matrix Λ ; in statements (vii)–(xii), $S = \text{scirc}(s_1, \dots, s_N)$ has eigenvalue matrix Λ . The following statements are true:*

- (i) $\{\sigma^{1-j}c_j\}_1^N$ is real $\iff \Lambda$ is centrohermitian,
- (ii) $\{\sigma^{1-j}c_j\}_1^N$ is imaginary $\iff \Lambda$ is skew-centrohermitian,
- (iii) C is Hermitian with $\{\sigma^{1-j}c_j\}_1^N$ real $\iff \Lambda$ is real centrosymmetric,
- (iv) C is Hermitian with $\{\sigma^{1-j}c_j\}_1^N$ imaginary $\iff \Lambda$ is real skew-centrosymmetric,
- (v) C is skew-Hermitian with $\{\sigma^{1-j}c_j\}_1^N$ real $\iff \Lambda$ is imaginary skew-centrosymmetric,
- (vi) C is skew-Hermitian with $\{\sigma^{1-j}c_j\}_1^N$ imaginary $\iff \Lambda$ is imaginary centrosymmetric,
- (vii) $\{\sigma^{j-1}s_j\}_1^N$ is real $\iff \Lambda$ is $[G]$ *-fixed,
- (viii) $\{\sigma^{j-1}s_j\}_1^N$ is imaginary $\iff \Lambda$ is skew- $[G]$ *-fixed,
- (ix) S is Hermitian with $\{\sigma^{j-1}s_j\}_1^N$ real $\iff \Lambda$ is real $[G]$ -fixed,
- (x) S is Hermitian with $\{\sigma^{j-1}s_j\}_1^N$ imaginary $\iff \Lambda$ is real skew- $[G]$ -fixed,
- (xi) S is skew-Hermitian with $\{\sigma^{j-1}s_j\}_1^N$ real $\iff \Lambda$ is imaginary skew- $[G]$ -fixed,
- (xii) S is skew-Hermitian with $\{\sigma^{j-1}s_j\}_1^N$ imaginary $\iff \Lambda$ is imaginary $[G]$ -fixed.

Proof. Recall from §2 that a circulant and a skew-circulant are interchanged by the diagonal unitary Y via the similarity transform $C = Y^*SY$, equivalently $S = YCY^*$. Being a similarity, it preserves the spectrum, so C and $S = YCY^*$ share the eigenvalue matrix Λ . Writing $C = \text{circ}(c_1, \dots, c_N)$, the first row of $S = YCY^*$ is $s_k = \sigma^{1-k}c_k$; hence the hypothesis that $\{\sigma^{1-j}c_j\}_1^N$ is real (respectively imaginary) is precisely the statement that the skew-circulant S is real (respectively imaginary). A direct calculation with Y , using $S^* = Y^*C^*Y$ and $S^T = Y^*C^TY$, establishes the following correspondence between the (skew-)Hermitian symmetry of C and the (skew-)symmetry of S :

$$C \text{ Hermitian} \iff \begin{cases} S \text{ symmetric} & (s \text{ real}), \\ S \text{ skew-symmetric} & (s \text{ imaginary}), \end{cases}$$

$$C \text{ skew-Hermitian} \iff \begin{cases} S \text{ skew-symmetric} & (s \text{ real}), \\ S \text{ symmetric} & (s \text{ imaginary}). \end{cases}$$

Statements (i)–(vi) now follow, in both directions, by chaining these equivalences with the matching part of Theorem 3.14 applied to S , which carries the same Λ ; every statement of Theorem 3.14 is itself an equivalence. For instance, in (iii): C is Hermitian with $\{\sigma^{1-j}c_j\}$ real $\iff S$ is real symmetric $\iff \Lambda$ is real centrosymmetric, by Theorem 3.14(v); in (i): $\{\sigma^{1-j}c_j\}$ is real $\iff S$ is real $\iff \Lambda$ is centrohermitian, by Theorem 3.14(i). The remaining cases (ii), (iv), (v), (vi) use parts (ii), (iv), (iii), (vi) of Theorem 3.14 respectively.

matrix class	circulant spectrum	skew-circulant spectrum
real	$[G]$ -fixed	centrohermitian
imaginary	skew- $[G]$ -fixed	skew-centrohermitian
complex symmetric	$[G]$ -fixed	centrosymmetric
complex skew-symmetric	skew- $[G]$ -fixed	skew-centrosymmetric
real symmetric	real $[G]$ -fixed	real centrosymmetric
imaginary symmetric	imaginary $[G]$ -fixed	imaginary centrosymmetric
real skew-symmetric	imaginary skew- $[G]$ -fixed	imaginary skew-centrosymmetric
imaginary skew-symmetric	real skew- $[G]$ -fixed	real skew-centrosymmetric
conditioned class	circulant spectrum	skew-circulant spectrum
sequence real	centrohermitian	$[G]$ -fixed
sequence imaginary	skew-centrohermitian	skew- $[G]$ -fixed
Hermitian, sequence real	real centrosymmetric	real $[G]$ -fixed
Hermitian, sequence imaginary	real skew-centrosymmetric	real skew- $[G]$ -fixed
skew-Hermitian, sequence real	imaginary skew-centrosymmetric	imaginary skew- $[G]$ -fixed
skew-Hermitian, sequence imaginary	imaginary centrosymmetric	imaginary $[G]$ -fixed

TABLE 1. The complete symmetry-to-persymmetry dictionary; every entry is an equivalence. Top panel: Theorems 3.7, 3.14 and 3.18. Bottom panel: the exceptional cases of Theorem 3.21, conditioned on the conjugated generating sequence— $\{\sigma^{1-j}c_j\}_1^N$ for a circulant, $\{\sigma^{j-1}s_j\}_1^N$ for a skew-circulant; note that each column then takes on the spectral classes of the other.

Statements (vii)–(xii) are dual. Now the matrix is a skew-circulant $S = \text{scirc}(s_1, \dots, s_N)$, and the circulant $C = Y^*SY$ has first row $c_k = \sigma^{k-1}s_k$, so $\{\sigma^{j-1}s_j\}_1^N$ is real (respectively imaginary) precisely when C is real (respectively imaginary). The same correspondence read in reverse— S Hermitian $\iff C$ real symmetric when c is real, and so on—lets the matching part of Theorem 3.7 apply, again in both directions, to C , which shares Λ with S . Thus (vii), (viii) use Theorem 3.7(i),(ii); (ix),(x) use (v),(iv); and (xi),(xii) use (iii),(vi). \square

Example 3.22. For $N = 4$, take $C = \text{circ}(a, be^{i\pi/4}, 0, be^{-i\pi/4})$ with a and b real. Then C is Hermitian, and with $\sigma = e^{i\pi/4}$ the conjugated sequence $\{\sigma^{1-j}c_j\}_1^4 = \{a, b, 0, -b\}$ is real; equivalently, $S = YCY^* = \text{scirc}(a, b, 0, -b)$ is real symmetric. Theorem 3.21(iii) then asserts a real centrosymmetric spectrum, and indeed $\Lambda = \text{diag}(a + \sqrt{2}b, a - \sqrt{2}b, a - \sqrt{2}b, a + \sqrt{2}b)$. Note that Λ is *not* $[G]$ -fixed unless $b = 0$: the exceptional cases genuinely depart from the $[G]$ -pattern of Theorems 3.7 and 3.18.

Table 1 collects the full dictionary established by Theorems 3.7, 3.14, 3.18 and 3.21.

3.6. Consequences for the singular value decomposition. Although our focus is the spectrum, it is worth recording briefly how the persymmetries above bear on the singular value decomposition. The underlying facts here are classical, and we claim no novelty for them; they are included only because the symmetry classification makes the structure of the singular values transparent.

Lemma 3.23. *Every circulant and every skew-circulant is a normal matrix.*

Proof. Since $FCF^* = \Lambda$, we have $C = F^*\Lambda F$, so C is unitarily similar to a diagonal matrix and is therefore normal. For a skew-circulant, Lemma 2.13 gives $\Lambda = FY^*SYF^*$, whence $S = (YF^*)\Lambda(YF^*)^*$ with YF^* unitary; thus S is also unitarily diagonalisable and hence normal. \square

Remark 3.24. Because a normal matrix is unitarily diagonalisable, its singular values are the moduli of its eigenvalues. For a circulant this is the familiar fact that the singular values are $|\lambda_j|$, the moduli of the discrete Fourier transform of the first row [2]; writing $\Lambda = |\Lambda|\Phi$ with the unitary phase matrix $\Phi = \text{diag}(\lambda_j/|\lambda_j|)$ (and $\lambda_j/|\lambda_j| := 1$ when $\lambda_j = 0$) yields the explicit decompositions $C = F^*|\Lambda|(F^*\Phi^*)^H$ and $S = (YF^*)|\Lambda|(YF^*\Phi^*)^H$. The one point we wish to add is that the

persymmetries of §3.3–3.4 pass intact to the singular values: since $|\cdot|$ annihilates both complex conjugation and sign, every spectral class of Theorems 3.7 and 3.14 forces $|\Lambda|$ to be $[G]$ -fixed (for circulants) or centrosymmetric (for skew-circulants). Hence the N singular values contain at most $\lfloor N/2 \rfloor + 1$ distinct values, obtainable from the reduced DCT-I/DST-I spectra of Remarks 3.12 and 3.17.

4. NUMERICAL EXPERIMENTS

The experiments serve two purposes. The first—the central one for this paper—is to confirm the classification of §3 directly: that each complex or imaginary symmetry class produces *exactly* the persymmetry of the spectrum predicted by Theorems 3.7, 3.14, 3.18 and 3.21. The second, smaller purpose is to confirm that the explicit closed-form expressions written down for the real symmetric and skew-symmetric special cases (Remarks 3.12 and 3.17) are numerically correct.

All computations were performed in double precision in NumPy [31]. Test matrices were generated with pseudorandom Gaussian entries constrained to the relevant symmetry class; reference spectra were obtained from a dense eigensolver and reference singular values from a dense SVD.

4.1. Verification of the classification. For each statement of Theorems 3.7, 3.14, 3.18 and 3.21 we draw a random matrix of the stated symmetry class and form its eigenvalue matrix Λ . Each statement predicts that Λ lies in a definite persymmetry class— $[G]$ -fixed, $[G]^*$ -fixed, centrosymmetric, centrohermitian, or a skew variant—possibly together with the eigenvalues being real or purely imaginary. Table 2 reports, for a representative selection spanning all four theorems, the maximum absolute residual of the predicted identity (for instance $\|G\Lambda^*G - \Lambda\|_\infty$ for a $[G]^*$ -fixed prediction, augmented by $\|\text{Im } \Lambda\|_\infty$ when the spectrum is predicted real). The experiments exercise the forward direction of each equivalence; the converse directions follow algebraically from the bijections of Lemmas 3.6 and 3.13 and are not separately sampled. Every residual sits at the level of round-off. The omitted statements behave identically: across all twenty-eight statements of §3, for N up to 1024 and many random trials, the largest residual observed was 1.4×10^{-12} .

Case	predicted spectral class	residual
Thm 3.7(ii) C imaginary, general	complex skew- $[G]^*$ -fixed	2.1×10^{-14}
Thm 3.7(vi) C imaginary, symmetric	imaginary $[G]$ -fixed	2.8×10^{-14}
Thm 3.14(ii) S imaginary, general	complex skew-centrohermitian	2.9×10^{-14}
Thm 3.14(iv) S imaginary, skew-sym.	real skew-centrosymmetric	2.1×10^{-14}
Thm 3.18(i) C complex, symmetric	complex $[G]$ -fixed	3.0×10^{-14}
Thm 3.18(iv) S complex, skew-sym.	complex skew-centrosymmetric	3.6×10^{-14}
Thm 3.21(iii) C Hermitian, $\{\sigma^{1-j}c_j\}$ real	real centrosymmetric	6.6×10^{-13}
Thm 3.21(xi) S skew-Herm., $\{\sigma^{j-1}s_j\}$ real	imaginary skew- $[G]$ -fixed	7.0×10^{-13}

TABLE 2. Direct verification of the spectral classification at $N = 512$: maximum absolute residual of the persymmetry identity predicted by each cited statement, over random matrices of the stated symmetry class. All twenty-eight statements were verified the same way; the largest residual over the full set was 1.4×10^{-12} for $N \leq 1024$.

4.2. The explicit real-case closed forms. The classification specialises, in the real symmetric and skew-symmetric cases, to explicit closed forms for the spectrum (Remarks 3.12 and 3.17). As a check on those expressions, Table 3 lists the maximum absolute deviation of each from a dense reference. The agreement is at the level of floating-point round-off: the $(m - 1)$ -point DST-I form of Remark 3.12 (real skew-symmetric circulant) and the DCT-I/DST-I form of Remark 3.17 (real skew-symmetric skew-circulant) reproduce the imaginary spectra exactly, and the singular values obtained as eigenvalue moduli (Remark 3.24) match the dense SVD.

N	sym. circ. (DCT-I)	skew-sym. circ. (DST-I, R.3.12)	skew-sym. scirc. (R.3.17)	SVD ($\sigma = \lambda $)
64	6.6×10^{-14}	3.6×10^{-14}	6.0×10^{-14}	2.3×10^{-14}
256	2.2×10^{-13}	2.0×10^{-13}	4.7×10^{-13}	6.2×10^{-14}
1024	7.2×10^{-13}	5.5×10^{-13}	6.3×10^{-12}	3.2×10^{-13}

TABLE 3. Maximum absolute deviation of the explicit real-case closed forms (Remarks 3.12, 3.17) and the singular values (Remark 3.24) from a dense eigen- or singular-value decomposition, double precision.

5. CONCLUSION

We have given a unified account of how the symmetry type of a circulant or skew-circulant—real, imaginary, symmetric, skew-symmetric, Hermitian or skew-Hermitian—fixes the persymmetry type of its eigenvalue matrix (each correspondence holding as an equivalence, not merely an implication), through the single device of the $(-)^{[G]}$ and $(-)^{[J]}$ fixing operators of Definition 2.5. The classification is exhaustive over these symmetry classes and, in contrast to earlier treatments, is carried out over the complex field.

A practical by-product is that, for most of the matrices considered, the entire spectrum is determined by about $N/2$ of its entries. In the real symmetric and skew-symmetric cases this recovers the reductions to fast cosine and sine transforms already exploited for real (skew-)circulants by Karner, Schneid and Ueberhuber [13, 14] and, more completely, by Liu et al. [15] and the subsequent work on block- and g -circulants [16, 17]; our contribution is to identify which persymmetry each complex symmetry class produces, the known real reductions being special cases. As recorded in §3.6, because these matrices are normal the same structure is inherited—classically—by their singular values, halving the number that need be computed.

Several questions remain. The spectral persymmetry of k -circulants for $k \neq \pm 1$, and of g - and block circulants, would extend the classification further, although the real, transform-based side of the latter is already developing rapidly [16, 17]. We anticipate the present results will be most useful where complex (skew-)circulants arise directly—for instance as preconditioners in ‘flexible’ iterative solvers whose preconditioner changes at each step [4].

STATEMENTS

Author contributions. The author has accepted responsibility for the entire content of this manuscript and approved its submission.

Use of large language models, AI and machine learning tools. Large language model (AI) tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript. An AI assistant was used to help reconstruct the L^AT_EX source from an earlier PDF of the author’s own work, to assist with copy-editing, formatting and preparation of the bibliography, to perform numerical verification of the stated results, and to assist with literature searches. All mathematical content—the definitions, theorems, proofs and conclusions—is the author’s own and was not generated by these tools. The author has checked and verified the entire manuscript and takes full responsibility for its content.

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